

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS BRANDED T-SHIRTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TIRUPUR CITY

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Abstract:

Marketing research is concerned with all those factors which have a direct impact upon the marketing of products and services. It is the study of any part of total marketing process. Marketing research is the function which links the customer, consumer and public to the marketer through information used to identify and define marketing opportunities and problems, generate refine and evaluate actions, monitor marketing performance and improve understanding of marketing as a process. In the existing business environment, markets are turbulent and customer needs are fast changing. Therefore, companies should select for ways to add value for their customer by offering products or services just the way they want it. When the customers has to choose from a larger number of options, features, pricing structures and various delivery methods, offering a unique product to every individual customer will go along way in adding value to the customer decision making process. The rich availability of raw materials, and its close proximity to Coimbatore, which is a major centre of cotton spinning industry in the country, provides Tirupur abundant and timely access to its basic raw materials. The objective of the study is (i) To study the factor that influences the purchase of product. (ii) To know the end user response towards the branded t-shirts. Tools like T-test, ANOVA test and Correlation were used. Major findings of the study are the Brand Image of the Product is strongly preferred by the respondents in the places of Tirupur, Coimbatore, Erode and Pollachi. More than 80% respondents were focusing on Advertisement, Brand Image, Comfort, Price and Quality while buying the products. The company has been able to create a strong position in the market and gain the trust of customers across the industry. This has been possible owing to their relentless pursuit of excellence and ability to fulfil even the most complex requirements of the customers in an efficient manner.

Key Words: Marketing, Customer, Business Environment, Decision Making Process & Brand Image

Introduction:

Customer satisfaction is defined as the behaviour that customers display in searching that they expect will satisfy their needs. It is the systematic gathering, recording and analyzing of data about problems connected with the market place. Marketing research is the function which links the customer, consumer and public to the marketer through information used to identify and define marketing opportunities and problems, generate refine and evaluate actions, monitor marketing performance and improve understanding of marketing as a process. Marketing research is concerned with all those factors which have a direct impact upon the marketing of products and services. It concentrates on the study of product planning and development, pricing, policies, effectiveness of personal selling, advertisement and sales promotion, competition and the entire area of buyer behaviour and attitudes in the market place. The study of customer satisfaction from various themes is the important once are discussed below:

About The Industry:

Tirupur is popularly known as "T-shirt City" of the country. It has come a long way from being a small cotton-marketing centre with a few ginning factories to become a prominent cluster of small and medium scale manufacturing enterprises gainfully engaged in the production export of a range of knitted apparels. The city's rapid growth can be attributed to the growth of textile industry. Textile industry is one of the main pillars supporting the Indian economy. It constitutes about 14% of industrial production, 20% of total export earnings 4% of GDP and provides direct employment to an estimated 35 million people. In spite of these, India's entire share in world textiles trade is still struggling at around 3%. About 45% of Indian garment exports are in the form of knitwear, and in this, Tirupur plays a pivotal role, generating as much as 90% of the knitted garment exports, in other words, about 4% of India's total export trade.

Literature Review:

Venkatesh and Menon (2010): in their study they analyzed the customer satisfaction based on the customer response towards the apparels. From this study it was inferred that the main underlying facts are sales support, purchase support, financial support and cost of ownership. Puranik (2009): Studied about "Consumer buying behaviour towards the branded apparels". The objective of the study was, to find out the level of

awareness of the consumer about the number of brands available in the market. The findings were the consumer aware about the product and purchase the same with ultimate brand awareness. Karthikeyan, Sundarraj (2011): “An investigation on consumer behaviour and preferences towards apparel, purchase by Indian consumers age 15 – 25”. In this study they focus on the consumer behaviour of young Indians in the age of 15 – 25 to understand and know their perception towards spending and to show a new path for the society and the industry for a sustainable environment. Namita Rajput, Subodh Kesharwani, Akanksha Khanna: Studied about “Consumers” Attitude towards Branded Apparels”. The objective of this paper is to analyze the significance of demographic profile of consumers affecting the purchase decision of branded garments and to observe from gender perspective the consumer awareness about different apparel brands available in the Indian market and also to find out whether there is a significant difference in total expenditure on branded apparels done by males and females. The results exhibit no significant differences in the brand awareness, shopping frequency and shopping expenditure between males and females.

Objectives of the Study:

Primary Objective:

- ✓ To study on customer satisfaction towards branded t-shirts.

Secondary Objectives:

- ✓ To study the factors that influences the purchase of product.
- ✓ To know the end user response towards the branded t-shirts.
- ✓ To identify the target market.
- ✓ To know the competency with other brands.

Scope for the Study:

Tirupur Textile Cluster has achieved increased sales over the past years. Due to the prevailing heavy competition in the market, an effort has been made to survey the customer level of satisfaction for Branded T-Shirts. A study with consistency required to comprehend the level of consumer awareness. The survey depends on the satisfaction of the respondents. In today’s world rapidly changing technology customer’s taste and preference are also characterized by rapid changes. To meet this challenging environment, a firm has to be constantly innovating needs and wants. Customers taste and preference provides invaluable items and guidelines for new technologies. Keeping in mind the conveniences of the customer’s, the company offer facilities, which in turn bring the customers to their door steps. Based on the customer response, suitable modifications can be carried out to increase the Market share as well as companies retail shop profit.

Research Methodology:

Research Design: The research design adopted for this study is descriptive study tries to discover answer to the question who, what, when, where and how. The research attempts to describe or define a subject, often by creating through this descriptive design can provide the decision makers with evidence that can lead to a course of action.

Data Collection: Primary data was collected through questionnaire. Secondary data was collected from company database.

Sampling Design: The concept of sampling also plays an important role in the process of identifying and understanding the market constructs that need to be investigated by the researcher. The basic idea of sampling is to select some elements from the population, and draw conclusion about the entire population.

Sample Size: The data collection was done with 120 customers.

Tools and Techniques:

- ✓ Simple percentage analysis
- ✓ T-test
- ✓ ANOVA test and
- ✓ Correlation

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

T-Test with Gender Groups:

(i) Advertisement:

Null Hypothesis: H_0 , There is no significant difference exists between Gender groups with respect to the advertisement.

Alternate Hypothesis: H_1 , There is significant difference exists between Gender groups with respect to the advertisement.

Table 2.3: Table showing the independent t-test within the gender groups with respect to the advertisement

	GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
ADVERTISEMENT	MALE	101	1.8317	1.04947	.10443
	FEMALE	19	1.4211	.50726	.11637

ADVERTISEMENT	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
								95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	5.098	.026	1.665	118	.099	.41063	.24662	-.07774	.89900
Equal variances not assumed			2.626	52.528	.011	.41063	.15636	.09695	.72431

Interpretation:

For the factor Advertisement, the significant value is less than 0.05 and hence rejects the null hypothesis H₀. i.e., there is a significant difference exists between Gender groups in the view of factor Advertisement. And the alternate hypothesis accepted.

(ii) Brand Image:

Null Hypothesis: H₀, There is no significant difference exists between Gender groups with respect to the brand image.

Alternate Hypothesis: H₁, There is significant difference exists between Gender groups with respect to the brand image.

Table 2.4: Table showing the independent t-test within the gender groups with respect to the brand image

	GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
BRANDIMAGE	MALE	101	1.8317	.94941	.09447
	FEMALE	19	1.6316	.49559	.11370

BRAND IMAGE	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
								95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	4.102	.045	.894	118	.373	.20010	.22385	-.24319	.64340
Equal variances not assumed			1.354	47.369	.182	.20010	.14782	-.09722	.49742

Interpretation:

For the factor Brand Image, the significant value is less than 0.05 and hence rejects the Null hypothesis H₀. i.e., there is a significant difference exists between Gender groups in the view of factor Brand Image. And the alternate hypothesis accepted.

(iii) Quality:

Null Hypothesis: H₀, There is no significant difference exists between Gender groups with respect to the quality.

Alternate Hypothesis: H₁, There is significant difference exists between Gender groups with respect to the quality.

Table 2.5: Table showing the independent t-test within the gender groups with respect to the quality

	GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
QUALITY	MALE	101	2.6139	.85989	.08556
	FEMALE	19	3.0526	.70504	.16175

QUALITY	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
								95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	3.869	.052	-2.094	118	.038	-.43877	.20958	-.85380	-.02374
Equal variances not assumed			-2.398	29.074	.023	-.43877	.18298	-.81297	-.06457

Interpretation:

For the factor Quality, the significant value is greater than 0.05 and hence accept the Null hypothesis H₀. i.e., there is no significant difference exists between Gender groups in the view of factor Quality.

(iv) Style:

Null Hypothesis: H₀, There is no significant difference exists between Gender groups with respect to the style.

Alternate Hypothesis: H₁, There is significant difference exists between Gender groups with respect to the style.

Table 2.6: Table showing the independent t-test within the gender groups with respect to the style

	GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
STYLE	MALE	101	2.1089	1.11266	.11071
	FEMALE	19	1.6316	.68399	.15692

STYLE	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
								95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	4.087	.045	1.803	118	.074	.47733	.26471	-.04686	1.00152
Equal variances not assumed			2.486	38.658	.017	.47733	.19204	-.08878	.86589

Interpretation:

For the factor Style, the significant value is less than 0.05 and hence rejects the Null hypothesis H₀. i.e., there is a significant difference exists between Gender groups in the view of factor Style. So, alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Anova with Respondents Place and Age Groups:

(i) Adidas:

Null Hypothesis: H₀, There is no significant difference exists between respondents Place and the factor Adidas.

Alternate Hypothesis: H₁, There is significant difference exists between respondents Place and the factor Adidas.

Table 2.7: Table showing the analysis of variance within the place with respect to the factor Adidas

ADIDAS	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
TIRUPUR	97	1.5551	.33387	.03390	1.4878	1.6224	1.00	2.58
COIMBATORE	12	1.4097	.11491	.03317	1.3367	1.4827	1.25	1.58
ERODE	8	1.3229	.13684	.04838	1.2085	1.4373	1.17	1.50
POLLACHI	3	1.4444	.33679	.19444	.6078	2.2811	1.25	1.83
Total	120	1.5223	.31485	.02874	1.4654	1.5792	1.00	2.58

ADIDAS	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.592	3	.197	2.044	.111
Within Groups	11.204	116	.097		
Total	11.797	119			

Interpretation:

For the factor Adidas, the significant value is greater than 0.05 and hence accept Null hypothesis H₀. i.e., there is no significant difference exists between respondents place in the view of factor Adidas.

(ii) Nike:

Null Hypothesis: H₀, There is no significant difference exists between respondents Place and the factor Nike.

Alternate Hypothesis: H₁, There is significant difference exists between respondents Place and the factor Nike.

Table 2.8: Table showing the analysis of variance within the place with respect to the factor Nike

NIKE	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
TIRUPUR	97	3.0756	.30715	.03119	3.0137	3.1375	1.92	4.00
COIMBATORE	12	3.1111	.28721	.08291	2.9286	3.2936	3.00	4.00
ERODE	8	3.1250	.29209	.10327	2.8808	3.3692	3.00	3.83
POLLACHI	3	3.0000	.00000	.00000	3.0000	3.0000	3.00	3.00
Total	120	3.0806	.29860	.02726	3.0266	3.1345	1.92	4.00

NIKE	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.049	3	.016	.179	.911
Within Groups	10.561	116	.091		
Total	10.610	119			

Interpretation:

For the factor Nike, the significant value is greater than 0.05 and hence the Null hypothesis H₀ is accepted. i.e., there is no significant difference exists between respondents place in the view of factor Nike.

(iii) PUMA:

Null Hypothesis: H₀, There is no significant difference exists between respondents Place and the factor Puma.

Alternate Hypothesis: H₁, There is a significant difference exists between respondents Place and the factor Puma.

Table 2.9: Table showing the analysis of variance within the place with respect to the factor Puma

PUMA	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
TIRUPUR	97	2.1856	.25727	.02612	2.1337	2.2374	1.58	3.00
COIMBATORE	12	2.1806	.22983	.06634	2.0345	2.3266	2.00	2.50
ERODE	8	2.1979	.29526	.10439	1.9511	2.4448	2.00	2.75
POLLACHI	3	2.0278	.04811	.02778	1.9083	2.1473	2.00	2.08
Total	120	2.1819	.25313	.02311	2.1362	2.2277	1.58	3.00

PUMA	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.075	3	.025	.382	.766
Within Groups	7.550	116	.065		
Total	7.625	119			

Interpretation:

For the factor Puma, the significant value is greater than 0.05 and hence accept the Null hypothesis H₀. i.e., there is no significant difference exists between respondents place in the view of factor Puma.

(iv) Reebok:

Null Hypothesis: H₀, There is no significant difference exists between respondents Place and the factor Reebok. Alternate Hypothesis: H₁, There is a significant difference exists between respondents Place and the factor Reebok.

Table 2.10: Table showing the analysis of variance within the place with respect to the factor Reebok

REEBOK	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
TIRUPUR	97	1.6753	.33625	.03414	1.6075	1.7430	1.00	2.33
COIMBATORE	12	1.4722	.17528	.05060	1.3609	1.5836	1.17	1.75
ERODE	8	1.4062	.38172	.13496	1.0871	1.7254	1.00	2.00
POLLACHI	3	1.6944	.33679	.19444	.8578	2.5311	1.50	2.08
Total	120	1.6375	.33484	.03057	1.5770	1.6980	1.00	2.33

REEBOK	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.904	3	.301	2.809	.043
Within Groups	12.439	116	.107		
Total	13.342	119			

Interpretation:

For the factor Brand name Reebok, the significant value is less than 0.05 and hence rejects the Null hypothesis H₀. i.e., there is a significant difference exists between respondents Place group and the factor Reebok. So, Null hypothesis H₀ is rejected.

Correlation:

Correlation refers to a scientific relationship between two variables. Furthermore, it is a measure of the strength and direction of that relationship. Two measures for each subject (or object) in the group are required.

Table 2.11: Table showing the correlation matrix for the factors

		ADVERTISEMENT	BRAND IMAGE	QUALITY	STYLE	PRICE
ADVERTISEMENT	Pearson Correlation	1	.713**	-.586**	.751**	.679**
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	120	120	120	120	120
BRANDIMAGE	Pearson Correlation	.713**	1	-.316**	.526**	.551**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	120	120	120	120	120
QUALITY	Pearson Correlation	-.586**	-.316**	1	-.673**	-.479**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	120	120	120	120	120
STYLE	Pearson Correlation	.751**	.526**	-.673**	1	.598**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	120	120	120	120	120
PRICE	Pearson Correlation	.679**	.551**	-.479**	.598**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	120	120	120	120	120

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Interpretation:

The five factors are tested for correlation. Pearsons correlation test was performed. All the above factors are both positively and negatively correlated with each others. The Brand Image, Style and Price are positively correlated with the Advertisement factor. And the Quality is negatively correlated with the factor Advertisement. Style and Price are positively correlated with the Brand Image. And Quality is negatively correlated with the factor Brand Image. The above all factors are negatively correlated with the factor Quality. The Advertisement, Brand Image and Price are positively correlated with the factor Style. And Advertisement, Brand Image and Style are positively correlated with the factor Price.

Table 2.28: Table showing the correlation matrix for the brands

		CRYSTAL	NIKE	ADIDAS	PUMA	REEBOK
CRYSTAL	Pearson Correlation	1	1.000**	-.078	.413**	-.012
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000	.198	.000	.446
	N	120	120	120	120	120
NIKE	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1	-.078	.413**	-.012
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000		.198	.000	.446
	N	120	120	120	120	120
ADIDAS	Pearson Correlation	-.078	-.078	1	.127	.779**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.198	.198		.084	.000
	N	120	120	120	120	120
PUMA	Pearson Correlation	.413**	.413**	.127	1	.292**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000	.084		.001
	N	120	120	120	120	120
REEBOK	Pearson Correlation	-.012	-.012	.779**	.292**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.446	.446	.000	.001	
	N	120	120	120	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Interpretation:

The five Brands are tested for correlation. Pearson’s correlation test was performed. The all the above Brands are both positively and negatively correlated with each others. The Brands Nike and Puma is positively and strongly correlated with the Brand Crystal, and Adidas and Reebok are negatively correlated. Crystal and Puma are positively correlated with the Brand Nike, and Adidas and Reebok are negatively correlated. Puma and Reebok are positively correlated with Brand Adidas. But Crystal and Nike are negatively correlated with Brand Adidas. Crystal, Nike, Adidas and Reebok all Brands are correlated with the Brand Puma. Adidas and Puma are positively correlated with Brand Reebok and Crystal, Nike are negatively correlated.

Findings:

- ✓ It was found from the above table that 51% of respondents were age group of 18-22 years, 33% of were 23-26 years, 12% of were 27-30 years, and 4% of respondents were from 31-33 years age.
- ✓ More than 80% respondents were focusing on Advertisement, Brand Image, Comfort, Price and Quality while buying the products.
- ✓ It was found from above that Advertisement, Brand Image, Quality and Style were impacts to the gender group for buying the products.
- ✓ It was found that at the place of Tirupur the Reebok and Nike Brands are more satisfied by the respondents.
- ✓ The Brand Image of the Product is strongly preferred by the respondents in the places of Tirupur, Coimbatore, Erode and Pollachi.
- ✓ There is a significant difference exists between Gender groups in the view of factor Brand Image. And the Null hypothesis is rejected.
- ✓ There is no significant difference exists between Gender groups in the view of factor Quality. And the Null hypothesis is accepted.
- ✓ The Brand Image, Style and Price are positively correlated with the Advertisement factor. And the Quality is negatively correlated
- ✓ The Advertisement, Brand Image and Price are positively correlated with the factor Style. And Advertisement, Brand Image and Style are positively correlated with the factor Price.
- ✓ Crystal and Puma are positively correlated with the Brand Nike, and Adidas and Reebok are negatively correlated.
- ✓ Adidas and Puma are positively correlated with Brand Reebok and Crystal, Nike are negatively correlated.

Suggestions:

- ✓ I suggest to the company, to focus on providing special discounts while purchasing and ordering the t-shirts for printing.

- ✓ And focus on Quality and Style of the product while printing.
- ✓ To make more and more products preferred by the customer to their retail outlets, based on the marketing potential.

Conclusion:

The company has been able to create a strong position in the market and gain the trust of customers across the industry. This has been possible owing to their relentless pursuit of excellence and ability to fulfil even the most complex requirements of the customers in an efficient manner. Timely delivery, latest technology, customer centric approach and competitive price are some factors that have contributed to their success. At the stage of primitive economy every individuals use different kind of brands due to the advancement of technology. Based on the feedback of the respondent, the customer preferring the product depends upon some major attributes like Advertisement, Brand Image, Quality and Style. The company major retail shop focus on these attributes for producing the product, which leads towards the success. This research result is not a standard form for a long time. It can be changeable according to the market potential. So, the company should update the market potential often through some researches then should produce the product.